

A STUDY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE OF ZOMATO'S MEDIA PRIVATE LIMITED IN TAMIL NADU

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Abstract:

This study examines the study on Capital Structure of Zomato's Media Private Limited in Tamil Nadu on a data of the period 2009-2023. Correlation and multiple Regressions are used to analysis the relationship between dependent variable (Debt Equity Ratio) and independent variable (Profitability, Return on Assets, Return on Equity and Solvency Ratio). This is concluding that Solvency Ratio and Profitability ratio have positively association with DER.

Key Words: Capital Structure, ROA, ROE, DER, Regression

Introduction:

Capital structure is the particular combination of debt and equity used by a company to finance its overall operations and growth. Equity capital arises from ownership shares in a company and claims to its future cash flows and profits. Capital structure refers to the combination of borrowed funds and owners' fund that a firm uses for financing its fund requirements. Herein, borrowed funds comprise of loans, public deposits, debentures, etc. and owners' fund comprise of preference share capital, equity share capital, retained earning etc. Capital structure is the mix of debt and equity on a company's balance sheet. It shows how much of a company is financed by creditors and owners, and also provides insights into the company's cost of capital-how much the capital in the business is costing the owners.

Capital structure refers to the composition or make up of long term sources of funds such as equity shares, preference shares, debentures and long term loans. The essence of capital structure problem is to decide the ratio of debt capital to equity capital. Capital structure decision is one of the important decision the chief financial officer of company should take. It should develop an appropriate or target capital structure which is most advantageous to the company. This can be done only when all those factors which are relevant to the company's capital structure decisions are properly analysed and balanced. The optimum capital structure is one that maximizes the market value of the firm. The capital structure may vary among industries and among companies within an industry. Since a number of factors influence the capital structure decision of a company the judgment of the person making the capital structure decision plays a crucial part. These factors are highly psychological, complex and qualitative.

Objectives:

- To identify the capital structure of Zomato's Media Private Limited.
- To identify the positive or negative relationship between the factors affecting the capital structure and the debt ratio.
- To find out the important variables that affect the debt ratio of the Zomato's Media Private Limited by using multiple regression.

Review and Literature:

Das & Swain, (2018) In their study they had tried to find out the capital structure of the firms and their impact on firm's performance. They have considered 50 manufacturing companies in their sample size. They have selected companies on different criteria like 20 companies on the basis of market capitalization, 20 companies on the basis of total assets employed and 10 companies on the basis of revenue and growth. They have considered the data of 10 years. In this research regression model is used for the analysis purpose. The various variables used in the study are ROA, ROE, ROCE, EPS, Current ratio, long term debt to total assets, total debt to total assets, debt equity ratio. The result of the study shows that there is significant relationship and the impact of capital structure on profitability and performance of the firm.

Khalaf, (2013) In his study has tried to investigate the relationship between capital structure and firm performance and found that there is negative relationship between capital structure and firm performance. In study the sample size of 45 manufacturing companies is considered. The data of 5 years is considered. Multiple regression analysis technique is used for the data analysis. ROA, profit margin, are performance indicator and short term debt to total assets, long term debt to total assets, total debt to equity is used as indicator of capital structure.

Mohamed & Inun Jariya, (2015) studied the “Effect of Capital Structure on profitability of Food and Beverage sectors in Sri Lanka” by taking 14 companies of the Beverage, Food & Tobacco industry and 24 companies from the Manufacturing industry. They conducted the study to find out the relationship between profitability of the listed Beverage, Food and Tobacco industry in Sri Lanka and capital structure and to recognize the impact of capital structure on the profitability of the Food and Tobacco industry and listed Beverage, in Sri Lanka. The study revealed that total debt to asset has a negative impact on return on equity and return on capital employed and is significant a 0.05 significance level whereas leverage, measured by total debt to equity shows a negative relationship but not significant. Total debt assets is also found out a negative impact on profitability measured by ROCE after controlling for LNS at 0.01 significant levels. It is clear that bpth the measures of leverage (TDA &TDE) have negative impact on both the measures of profitability (ROE &ROCE). The value is less than 0.01 for the all the cases. Therefore, it could be concluded that at 1% significance level, leverage/debt capital has a negative impact on the profitability of beverage, food and tobacco sector firms listed on Sri Lanka

Goyal (2013) made a study entitled “Impact of capital structure on performance of listed public sector banks in India” with the purpose to measure the impact of capital structure on banking performance. He has taken 19 PSU banks listed on NSE as the sample for the study. It is concluded that the profitability measured by return on equity reveals an average of 17.98 percent with median of 18.19 percent. This picture may suggest a good performance during the period under the study. The average value of TDC variable is 18.66 with median of 17. This position reveals that the banks are financially leveraged with a large percentage of total debt being short-term. The average growth is 21.29 and the average firm size is measured by logarithm of assets.

Singh & Bagga, (2019) They have found from their study done to find out the effect of capital structure on the profitability of the firms that there is significant relationship between the capital structure and the profitability of the firm and the capital structure has positive impact on the firm's profitability. The study was conducted on nifty 50 companies listed on NSE. The data of 10 years was considered. The performance indicators used in study are ROA, ROE, ratio of total liabilities to total assets, EBIT, TANG [asset tangibility]. Tax, Liquidity, business risk. The technique used in study in descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple panel data regression model. Four different regression models are used to study the relationship between the capital structure and the profitability.

Methodology:

The study is based on secondary data. The data collected from annual report of company concerned listed in the balance sheet. The study has been undertaken in Zomato's Media Private Limited, the above data was collected on the basis of their consistency of performance, data availability and favourable accounting figures of this company.

Regression Model:

The Multiple Regression models have been followed to test the empirical relationship between the debt equity ratio and characteristics of the firm.

$$Y=a+b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3+b_4X_4.....(1)$$

Table of Variables:

Table 1

S.No	Ratio	Variable	Formula
1	Debt Equity Ratio	Dependent Variable	Total Current Liabilities / Total Shareholder's funds
2	Solvency Ratio	Independent Variable	Profit and Loss After Tax / Total shareholder's fund *100
3	Profitability Ratio	Independent Variable	Total Assets / Total Shareholder's funds *100
4	Return on equity	Independent Variable	Current Assets – Current Liabilities
5	Return on Assets	Independent Variable	Profit and Loss After Tax / Total Assets *100

Result and Discussion:

Results of Correlation:

Table 2

Variable	R	R ²
Solvency Ratio	0.834	0.695
Profitability	0.997	0.994
Return on Equity	0.705	0.497
Return on Assets	0.473	0.223

** Correlation is significant at the 1% level (2 tailed)

Table 2, above represents the relationship between the various independent and dependent variables used in this study. From this table that the variables solvency ratio has strong positive association with debt equity ratio. Profitability has highly associated with debt equity ratio. Return on equity has negatively associated with debt equity ratio.

Results of the Regression:

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	0.998 ^a	0.997	0.995	0.0179

Predictors: (Constant), Return on Assets, Profitability, Return on Equity, Solvency Ratio

The model summary table illustrates the magnitude of the variance in the dependent variables as described by the independent variables. The value of the R-Square is 0.995, which is approximately the dependent variable 89.8% variance of the “Debt Equity Ratio” are explained by independent variables of capital structure ratios.

ANOVA:

Table 4

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	0.916	5	0.183	568.078	0.000 ^b
Residual	0.003	9	0.00		
Total	0.919	14			

- a. Dependent variable : Debt Equity Ratio
- b. Predictors : (Constant), Return on Assets, Profitability, Return on Equity, Solvency Ratio

ANOVA test to find out whether the regression model is valid or not. F-Statistics is 568.078 which are very high and have a significant value less than 5% which indicates that the testing of ANOVA is highly significant and that the model is valid from the given predictors.

Regression coefficients of Zomato’s Media Private Limited:

Table 5

Variables	Model
(Constant)	
Un-Standardized co-efficient	-0.545
Standard error	0.353
T-value	-1.543
P-value	0.157
Solvency Ratio	
Un-Standardized co-efficient	0.013
Standard error	0.010
T-value	1.389
P-value	0.198
Profitability	
Un-Standardized co-efficient	0.692
Standard error	0.166
T-value	4.163
P-value	0.002
Return on Equity	
Un-Standardized co-efficient	1.225
Standard error	0.000
T-value	1.815
P-value	0.103
Return on Assets	
Un-Standardized co-efficient	-0.024
Standard error	0.020
T-value	-1.203
P-value	0.260

The parameter of the regression model above the table is related. The table 5 shows the significance of the individual independent variable in interpreting the dependent variable. The un-standardized co-efficient (B) value shows the magnitude and relationship between dependent variable debt equity ratio and independent variables of capital structure ratios, if the value is positive relationship between the predictor and the dependent variable. If the value is negative relationship between the predictor and the dependent variables. The regression co-efficient profitability significant association with debt equity ratio. It means Zomato’s Media Private Limited earned stable profitability. The regression co-efficient other independent variables are negatively associated with debt equity ratio.

Conclusion:

The purpose of this Research study is to investigate the Capital Structure of Zomato's Media Private Limited for this purpose Zomato's Media Private Limited has been selected from Tamil Nadu as study sample size and data is collected (2009-2023) and processed by using statistical tools. This study found that the Profitability (0.997) and Solvency Ratio (0.834) have positively significant with DER, Return on equity (-0.705) has negatively correlated with DER.

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